

THE INFLUENCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGY AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract. Modern technology has significantly impacted the tourism industry, transforming the way tourists plan, experience, and share their journeys. AI-powered chatbots, big data analytics, and virtual reality have revolutionized the industry, providing personalized recommendations and insights into customer behavior. However, the increasing reliance on technology can lead to a discrepancy between expectations and reality, requiring stakeholders to strike a balance between technological advancements and maintaining personal interactions. In Uzbekistan, AI and modern technologies have the potential to enhance the visitor experience and drive economic growth. This paper analyses these potentials like Chatbot services in multiple languages which can provide instant information on attractions, accommodations, and transportation options, while AI-powered algorithms can analyze vast amounts of data to gain insights into tourist trends and satisfaction levels. However, the reliance on technology has also led to challenges, such as over-reliance on online reviews, deceptive reviews, and disruptions in traditional hotel industries. To mitigate these issues, local businesses must adapt by integrating technology seamlessly into the travel experience, prioritizing human customer care, providing clear information about personal data usage.

Keywords: modern technologies, artificial intelligence, tourism industry, positive impact, negative impact.

Аннотация. Современные технологии существенно повлияли на туристическую индустрию, изменив то, как туристы планируют свои путешествия, получают от них впечатления и делятся ими. Чат-боты на базе искусственного интеллекта, аналитика больших данных и виртуальная реальность произвели революцию в отрасли, предоставляя персонализированные рекомендации и информацию о поведении клиентов. Однако растущая зависимость от технологий может привести к несоответствию между ожиданиями и реальностью, требуя от заинтересованных сторон соблюдения баланса между технологическими достижениями и поддержанием личного взаимодействия. В Узбекистане искусственный интеллект и современные технологии могут улучшить качество обслуживания посетителей и способствовать экономическому росту. Сервисы чат-ботов на нескольких языках предоставляют мгновенную информацию о достопримечательностях, вариантах размещения и транспорта, в то время как алгоритмы на базе искусственного интеллекта анализируют огромные объёмы данных, чтобы получить представление о тенденциях развития туризма и уровне удовлетворённости. Однако зависимость от технологий также привела к возникновению проблем, таких как чрезмерная зависимость от онлайн-обзоров, вводящие в заблуждение отзывы и сбои в традиционной гостиничной индустрии. Чтобы смягчить эти проблемы, местные предприятия должны адаптироваться, органично интегрируя технологии в процесс путешествий, уделяя приоритетное внимание заботе о клиентах, предоставляя чёткую информацию об использовании персональных данных.

Ключевые слова: современные технологии, искусственный интеллект, индустрия туризма, положительное влияние, отрицательное воздействие.

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar turizm sohasiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatdi, sayyohlarning rejalashtirish, tajriba va sayohatlarini baham ko'rish usullarini o'zgartirdi. Sun'iy intellekt orqali ishlaydigan chatbotlar, katta miqdordagi ma'lumotlar tahlili, va virtual olam turizm sohasini ham rivojlantirishga ulgurdi. Biroq, texnologiyaga bo'lgan ishonchning ortishi kutilgan natija va haqiqat o'rtasidagi tafovutga olib kelishi mumkin, bu esa manfaatdor tomonlardan texnologik yutuqlar va shaxsiy o'zaro ta'sirlar o'rtasida muvozanatni saqlashni talab qiladi. O'zbekistonda sun'iy intellekt va zamonaviy texnologiyalar tashrif buyuruvchilar tajribasini oshirish va iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash imkoniyatiga ega. Bir nechta tillardagi Chatbot xizmatlari diqqatga sazovor joylar, turar joylar va transport imkoniyatlari haqida tezkor ma'lumot beradi, SI bilan ishlaydigan algoritmlar esa sayyohlik tendentsiyalari va qoniqish darajasi haqida ma'lumot olish uchun juda ko'p ma'lumotlarni tahlil qiladi. Biroq, texnologiyaga tayanish, shuningdek, onlayn sharhlarga haddan tashqari ishonish, aldanchi sharhlar va an'anaviy mehmonxona sanoatidagi uzilishlar kabi muammolarga olib keldi. Ushbu muammolarni yumshatish uchun mahalliy korxonalar texnologiyani sayohat tajribasiga muammosiz qo'shish, mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatishni birinchi o'ringa qo'yish, shaxsiy ma'lumotlardan foydalanish to'g'risida aniq ma'lumot berish orqali moslashishlari kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy texnologiyalar, sun'iy intellekt, turizm sanoati, ijobiy ta'sir, salbiy ta'sir.

Introduction

The influence of modern technology on tourism has been colossal, shaping the industry in various aspects. Advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, and virtual reality (VR) have revolutionized the way tourists plan, experience, and share their journeys. For instance, AI-powered chatbots assist travelers in searching for and booking flights and accommodations, providing personalized recommendations based on their preferences. Big data analytics enable the tourism industry to gain insights into customer behavior and trends. Additionally, VR technologies offer immersive experiences that allow potential travelers to virtually explore destinations before making a reservation, enhancing their decision-making process. While modern technology has brought numerous advantages to the tourism industry, it is important to consider the potential downsides. With the increasing reliance on technology, there is a risk of reducing the human touch and discrepancy between expectations and reality may occur. Therefore, it is necessary for stakeholders in the tourism sector to strike a balance between technological advancements and maintaining the essence of personal interactions and inclusivity in the industry.

Research Methodology

The research paper uses the data collection, content analysis and mixed methods to competitively analyze and summarize the information provided. The paper uses data collection method to gather adequate reliable information to supplement the paper as well as support the approaches of authors. Content analysis method is used to analyze ample of resources in order to provide the paper with relevant and reliable data. Mixed method is used to synthesize the collected data coupled with coherently linking the particles of the paper appropriately.

The Implementation of Modern Technologies in Tourism Industry

Modern technologies have revolutionized the tourism industry, being used in many different ways, and have already become a significant part of it. "From the initial planning stages to the actual trip, advanced technologies are deployed in various ways." (Dimitrios & Rob, 2008).

Firstly, online travel platforms and mobile applications have simplified the process of finding and booking accommodations, flights, and activities, allowing travelers to conveniently customize their itineraries. Additionally, “augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) technologies have emerged as powerful tools, providing immersive experiences and virtual tours of popular tourist destinations” (Zsarnoczky, 2017). The utilization of Big Data and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms assists in predicting travel trends, enhancing safety measures, and facilitating targeted marketing campaigns. “Artificial intelligence, robotics, and service automation are extensively employed across multiple industries. Intelligent systems and tourism work in ideally, given the complexity of decision-making connected to travel. They can help with decision-making and have a big impact on travelers' information searches by gathering and analyzing data about users' individual needs. Artificial intelligence has therefore already been somewhat used in a number of tourism-related sectors.” (Zlatanov & Popersku, 2019). Undeniably, modern technologies have revolutionized the tourism industry, making it more accessible, efficient, and tailored to the needs and preferences of contemporary travelers as shown in the figure 1:

FIGURE 1

The usage of modern technologies and AI in tourism

Note: Data on the diagram is collected from websites: www.interglobe.com, www.refrine.com and www.techtarget.com.

Discussions: Positive and Negative Impacts of Modern Technology on Tourism

Positive Impacts

The tourism business has benefited considerably from modern technologies, which have a number of good effects. According to Zlatanov & Popersku, the tourist and hospitality industries have undergone significant transformation as a result of the revolution brought about by the advent of ICTs. Robots, artificial intelligence, and service automation have opened up a world of new possibilities for travel agencies. A novel kind of intelligence called artificial intelligence is able to combine several concepts at once. (2019). Thanks to the widespread use of cellphones and internet access, tourists can now plan and conduct research for their journeys more effectively. There is no need to call or physically visit travel agents when reservations can be made easily online. For

instance, AI and modern technologies have the potential to revolutionize the tourism industry in Uzbekistan, offering numerous opportunities for enhancing the visitor experience and driving economic growth. According to Arsenijevic & Jovic, one way AI could be implemented is through chatbot services in multiple languages, enabling tourists to receive instant information on attractions, accommodations, transportation options, and more. These intelligent virtual assistants can also provide personalized recommendations based on individual preferences and previous interactions. (2019). Moreover, enormous volumes of data from diverse sources, like as social media sites and internet reviews, can be analyzed by AI-powered algorithms to provide insights into traveler trends, behavior patterns, and satisfaction levels. Tourism authorities can use these information to better understand their target market and make well-informed decisions about resource allocation, marketing tactics, and infrastructure development. Additionally, technology-based solutions such as virtual reality (VR) tours can allow potential tourists to explore Uzbekistan's cultural heritage sites remotely before making travel commitments. Furthermore, AI-enabled facial recognition systems could streamline immigration processes at airports while ensuring security measures are upheld. With the implementation of AI and modern technologies in its tourism sector, Uzbekistan has a unique opportunity to establish itself as a cutting-edge destination that efficiently caters to the needs of tech-savvy travelers while simultaneously preserving its rich cultural heritage. GPS gadgets and navigation apps make it easier to explore destinations and less stressful to get lost. Social media sites also allow passengers to discuss their experiences, which might yield insightful information and suggestions for other travels. According to Andrei & Stan, Emerging technologies help to reduce costs, and more than that they are designed to help protect the environment (2010). The widespread adoption of contemporary technology has transformed the travel and tourism sector, enabling improved accessibility, effectiveness, and ease of use for tourists from all over the world.

Negative Influences

Modern technology has undoubtedly revolutionized the way we travel, with online booking platforms, GPS navigation systems, and social media influencing every aspect of our trips. However, the reliance on technology in the tourism industry has also led to some negative impacts. One of the major concerns is the over-reliance on online reviews and ratings, which can sometimes be manipulated or biased, leading to misinformation for travelers. According to Dimitrios & Peter, the rise in social media and online reviews has strengthened the influence of user-generated material, which frequently leads to reviews that are deceptive and information overload. This discrepancy between expectations and reality can lead to visitor unhappiness, harming the reputation of both businesses and locations (2015). Additionally, the rise of online vacation rental platforms has disrupted traditional hotel industries, causing a decrease in revenue for many local businesses. Furthermore, the constant connectivity afforded by technology means that visitors are often more focused on capturing the perfect Instagram moment rather than fully immersing themselves in the destination's culture and experiences. Overall, while technology has brought convenience and efficiency to the tourism industry, it has also brought about challenges that need to be addressed for the betterment of the travel experience. As technology continues to advance, it is crucial for the tourism industry to find a balance between embracing innovation and preserving the authenticity of travel experiences. Local businesses must adapt to the changing landscape by leveraging technology to enhance customer experiences while still maintaining the unique charm of their destinations. By finding ways to integrate technology seamlessly into the travel experience, businesses can cater to the evolving needs of modern travelers while also preserving the cultural

richness that makes each destination special. The negative impacts of modern technology and AI on tourism can be mitigated by implementing various solutions. "Prioritizing the human element in customer care by making sure that there are always qualified people on hand to help travelers with any problems or inquiries is one strategy to address this problem. Giving travelers clear information about how their personal data is being used and getting their consent before collecting any data is another way to solve the problem" (Tsaih & Hsu, 2018). Furthermore, it's critical to keep an eye on how tourism-related technology is affecting the environment and work to cut waste and carbon emissions. The detrimental effects of AI and contemporary technology on tourism can be reduced by resolving these problems and putting these answers into practice, resulting in improvement of visitors' experiences in general.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Artificial intelligence (AI) and modern technology have had a significant impact on the travel and tourism sector, both positively and negatively. Positively, thanks to technological improvements like mobile apps that offer real-time travel updates and online booking platforms, travel has become much more efficient and convenient. AI has also made it possible to customize travel experiences, including customized customer care and recommendations. However, there are drawbacks to technology use in tourism as well, including the loss of jobs and the growing discrepancy of information due to automation. Investing in education and training for individuals impacted by job displacement and putting laws in place to guarantee ethical AI use in business are two ways to lessen these drawbacks. Overall, the potential benefits of modern tech and AI in tourism outweigh the challenges, but careful consideration and strategic planning are necessary to navigate the transition successfully.

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